

EFFICIENCY ENHANCEMENT IN PLASMONIC IBC SOLAR CELLS

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ABSTRACT: Silicon solar cells dominate photovoltaics but suffer from poor interaction with light. This work reports on progress regarding both spectral conversion and improved light interaction with the LIMA design [1]. This combines an efficient interdigitated back-contact (IBC) solar cell [2] with a silicon quantum dot (Si-QD) [3] to optimize the spectral distribution of the incident spectrum, and finally a front-side plasmon layer to optimize light interaction. Reflectivity after thickness and process optimization for a thin Ag layer and a Si_3N_4 shows that plasmonic particle layers reduce reflectivity compared with an IBC with only a Si_3N_4 anti-reflective coating layer. There is an increasing of the quantum efficiency in the infrared zone but losses remain in the UV zone which needs to be addressed.

Keywords: High efficiency solar cells, Plasmonic particle layer, Quantum dot, Interdigitated Back Contact

1 INTRODUCTION

To further improve electrical and optical performance and to reduce the cost of photovoltaic electricity there is an ongoing trend towards ever thinner solar cells. However, indirect bandgap semiconductors like silicon tend to absorb less light and therefore generate less photocurrent when their layer thickness is reduced further.

Concerning the spectral conversion technique, this work uses a silicon quantum dot (Si-QD) layer to downshift incident radiation to longer wavelengths better suit to the solar cell. This is because whereas light at short wavelengths is absorbed close to the surface due to the greater absorption coefficient for high energy photons, the down-shifted radiation is absorbed more uniformly throughout the cell and suffers less from surface losses.

To improve light interaction, the Si-QD layer is coated with a plasmonic particle layer (PPL). This PPL plays the role of texturing but without increasing the effective surface area and surface recombination, that requires particularly good surface passivation in textured cells. The plasmon layer in the LIMA design does this principally by light scattering, as opposed to surface plasmon effects leading to high localized absorption coefficients as have been proposed for other designs [4]. The present approach builds on published results comparing front and back geometries [5].

Preliminary studies [6] have optimized metallic nanoparticle (MNP) size and distribution from the standpoint of available fabrication processes, leading to an optimum design fabricated on bare silicon substrates. This concluded that a Ag self-aggregation method was the most suitable at a temperature of 500°C.

This work reports on subsequent integration of the self-aggregation fabrication process with two changes. These are development on a Si_3N_4 film [7] deposited in a crystalline Si substrate for a range of Ag precursor film thicknesses and significantly lower anneal temperature below 300°C maximum in order to avoid device degradation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Fabrication process

The layer of silver nanoparticles used for these experiments were fabricated depositing a thin Ag layer of different thicknesses on a crystalline Si substrate using a Pfeiffer Vacuum Classic 500 evaporator followed by a thermal annealing at different temperatures in a Carbolite oven at different annealing times. No cleaning step was necessary as samples were inspected to be clean.

First set of samples were fabricated to optimize the Ag precursor thickness and annealing parameters. Following this PPL fabrication development, a second set of samples were fabricated to optimize the thickness of the Si_3N_4 coat on the crystalline Si substrate. Table I summarizes the different parameter ranges for the plasmon fabrication on Si_3N_4 coated crystalline Si substrate.

Table I: Parameter values used to fabricate plasmon samples on a Si_3N_4 coated crystalline Si substrates

Set	Precursor thicknesses (nm)	Annealing times (h)	Annealing temp. (°C)	Si_3N_4 thickness (nm)
1	3, 6, 8, 9, 10 and 12	1, 2 and 3	200 and 300	100
2	3 and 6	1	200	60, 64, 69, 74, 80, 85 and 100

2.2 Characterization

Particle size and distribution were characterized by high resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM), using a Hitachi S-4500 SEM. These images were analyzed using de Fiji implementation of image processing software ImageJ [8].

Samples were characterized optically using a FTIR Hyperion Vertex 80, yielding normal incidence reflectivity spectra for wavelengths from 345nm to 1250nm.

Fully integrated LIMA devices, PPL deposited on an IBC solar cell, were characterized with a Solar Cell Spectral Response Measurement System (PV Measurements QE7) for quantum efficiency and reflectivity measurements at normal incidence were

carried out in a Perkin Elmer Lambda 35 UV/Vis spectrophotometer in the spectral range between 300 and 1100nm.

The efficiency of the resulting LIMA device is characterized under AM1.5G simulated sunlight carried out by a Sun 200 Solar Simulators from ALBET Technologies.

3 RESULTS

Optimizing the PPL we observe that lower reflectivity is achieved for lower Ag thickness and, crucially, for low fabrication compatible temperature and time. Analysis of SEM micrographs of these samples shows an increase of particle density and decrease of particle size with decreasing Ag precursor thickness. An optimum in terms of minimum reflectivity is obtained for a 3nm Ag precursor, annealed at 200°C for 1 hour.

Figure 1: FTIR reflectivity measurements from samples with 3nm (1h annealing) Ag precursor thickness and without Ag on 60nm (top left), 64nm (bottom left) and 69nm (bottom) Si₃N₄ layer thicknesses

Figure 1 shows the measured reflectivities of a set of samples of the three best Si₃N₄ thicknesses, using the optimum PPL deposition parameters which are 3nm Ag annealed at 200°C for 60 minutes.

Using these results, the second set of samples is fabricated for the Si₃N₄ optimization. Figure 2 compares FTIR measurements of the optimum PPL and Si₃N₄ design, showing reduced reflectivity. Figure 3 shows the SEM images of these samples and how the particle density increases on a thinner Si₃N₄ layer.

Figure 2: FTIR reflectivity measurements from samples with 3nm (1h annealing) Ag precursor thickness on 60nm, 64nm and 69nm Si₃N₄ layer thicknesses.

Using ImageJ for particle analysis for the optimized thickness for the Si₃N₄ layer (Figure 3(c)), from a 3nm Ag precursor thickness, it is found that it has a 13nm of average particle diameter and 32.2% of area coverage.

Figure 3: SEM images from samples with 3nm (1h annealing at 200°C) Ag precursor thickness on (a) 60nm, (b) 64nm and (c) 69nm Si₃N₄ substrate thicknesses

From the results of the first stage optimization, a PPL is fabricated on an integrated IBC solar cell, consisting the full LIMA design. Figure 4 shows improvement external quantum efficiency (EQE) in the infrared region ascribe to the PPL scattering mechanism. For this integrated device, a 1% relative improvement in efficiency is obtained.

Figure 4: Quantum efficiency and total reflectivity before and after fabricating a PPL layer on an integrated IBC solar cell

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Plasmonic particle layer

We fabricated the plasmonic particle layer looking to minimize the reflection on the surface so maximize the light interaction with underlying solar cell. Of the series of samples made, the PPL with 3nm Ag precursor thickness has the best (lowest) reflectivity response.

4.2 Si₃N₄ substrate

Optimization of the Si₃N₄ layer results in the decreasing of reflectivity by the PPL in every sample fabricated. Figure 1 compares samples with and without the PPL implementation on the three best Si₃N₄ layer thicknesses, as Figure 2 shows the sample with lowest reflectivity.

4.3 Plasmonic particle layer integration

An optimized PPL is fabricated on an IBC solar cell (LIMA design). Figure 4 shows the EQE and reflectivity

of IBC LIMA designs with and without PPL. We see an increase in the infrared (IR) wavelength range corresponding to the decrease in reflectivity. This can be ascribed to the light scattering of the MNP on the solar cell. It is not well understood why there is poor agreement between the EQE between 550nm and 600nm, and the reflectivity over the same wavelength range: the EQE with MNPs decreases more than can be explained by the increase in reflectivity. It is proposed that light absorption losses linked to the MNP are the main problem.

As Figure 4 shows, below 550nm EQE decreases. This is due to the light losses of the MNP. The main mechanism responsible for these losses is the Fano interference between the incident light beam and plasmonic MNP luminescence [9]. This may be minimized in further work by tuning the refractive index of material encasing the MNP, and adjusting the MNP geometry.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Reflectivity measurements from different MNP layers have been used to design an optimum PPL with a low temperature PPL fabrication method. These results were used to optimize the fabrication of a Si₃N₄ layer with a PPL. Reflectivity measurements from different Si₃N₄ were used to obtain the optimum layer thickness.

The results from the fabrication method for low temperature PPL are used to fabricate an integrated LIMA design IBC solar cell showing a 1% relative improvement in efficiency. Improvement in the EQE is correlated with the increase of reflectivity in the IR wavelength range. Light losses and Fano resonances interference appear to explain the loss in the visible and ultraviolet wavelength range.

Further experimental results will be necessary to address the losses in the integrated IBC solar cell LIMA device.

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